

AI4Life & BioImage Archive FAIR AI Workshop

Summary of recommendations

Workshop participants – compiled by Teresa Zulueta-Coarasa

The development, reproducibility, and reuse of AI models rely on having open access to useful, annotated datasets that adhere to the **FAIR** principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability). One of the goals of the **AI4Life** project is to improve the **BioImage Archive's** (BIA) support for image annotations as part of AI-ready datasets and to develop annotation standards for the community. To this end, a virtual workshop was held on the 24th and 25th of January with 45 community experts from various backgrounds, including data generators, annotators, curators, AI researchers, and software developers. Thanks to the outstanding chairs and engaged participants, the workshop sessions resulted in a series of recommendations to develop annotation standards for the community, and to improve the submission, presentation, and retrieval of AI-ready images and annotations from the BIA.

The devil is in the metadata: towards a recommended metadata standard

The participants unanimously agreed on the importance of having a recommended metadata standard to facilitate the reuse of image and annotation data. One of the most immediate blockers developers encounter when reutilizing datasets is the lack of clear copyright permissions. Therefore, a focus must be put on specifying the type of license the images and the annotations are under, with a preference towards open licenses that encourage reuse, such as **CC0** and **CC BY**.

Another clear priority was access to the annotation's provenance, covering the following questions:

- Who are the authors?
- Were the annotations created by experts or crowdsourced?
- When were the annotations made?
- What software was used to generate the annotations, and what protocols were used for consensus and quality assurance?
- Were the annotations produced manually, predicted by an algorithm, or curated from a prediction?
- From what source image did the annotations originate? The association between images and annotations should be made explicit and not use only the file name.

A related topic of discussion was the possibility of storing an annotation quality confidence level. Suggested metrics for this are self-reported confidence, the variance among several annotators, or the number of years of experience of the annotator.

Regarding biological information, there was widespread support for the use of ontologies and controlled vocabularies to make data findable and interoperable. To facilitate the reuse of data by researchers from different fields that may not share a scientific vocabulary, several participants suggested having a one-line sentence describing the biological application of the dataset, similar to the datasets on the [Broad Bioimage Benchmark Collection](#).

Versioning was also extensively discussed in the workshop. Incremental versions must have accompanying metadata with timestamps and a pointer to the previous version. It is important to preserve the credit to the original annotators.

Another type of metadata that was deemed important is the AI models trained using the dataset, so datasets can point to specific models in repositories like the [BioImage Model Zoo](#) and vice versa.

Metadata should also indicate the annotation type (e.g., counts), which images from the dataset were annotated, and what percentage of the data has been annotated from what is available. This latter point is important to distinguish if the absence of annotations means that there is nothing of interest for a specific task or if simply part of the dataset has not been annotated.

Spatial information for non-pixel annotations (e.g., counts of items in a region of interest), including physical measurements or the region that has been annotated, needs to be recorded. Furthermore, any transformations required to link the images to the annotations, such as rotations and translations, should be included as metadata to ensure that the spatial scales match. We also need to account for the possibility of storing multiple types of spatial information for the same instance (e.g., for the same cell: cell segmentation and coordinates of transcription sites).

Finally, general image metadata needs to be stored. The BIA has adopted [REMBI](#) (Recommended Metadata for Biological Images) as its metadata model, which covers most of the points discussed in the workshop.

Formats: next step, next generation

Another main topic of the workshop was to agree on what file formats and dataset structures are the most useful for sharing and reusing annotation data. Several formats used in the community were carefully considered and the following emerged as the preferred options:

Formats for images and pixel/voxel annotations:

The workshop participants overwhelmingly agreed that **Next-Generation File Format** (NGFF) specifications from the Open Microscopy Environment (OME) are one of the best ways to store and serve AI data. NGFFs such as OME-Zarr are open, which increases interoperability. OME-Zarr is also cloud-ready, scalable, and annotations such as segmentation masks can be packaged with the image data allowing provenance tracking. There are also several OME-Zarr visualisation tools for raw data and annotations and tools for format conversion.

Another useful format for annotation data, used in other fields but relatively new for bioimages, is **COCO** (Common Objects in Context). COCO has multiple annotation types, like segmentations and classes, that are saved in JSON, and it is language agnostic. However, COCO was developed with computer-vision tasks in mind, thus its performance on multi-dimensional bioimages needs to be examined first.

Formats for tables:

Current developments in the NGFF community are concentrating on developing table annotation support. One of the options being considered are **AnnData** objects, which store annotated matrices in memory and on disk. Importantly, some participants raised the necessity to export tables to CSV or TSV as portability to statistical tools is required for some applications.

Formats for geometrical annotations:

Another specification widely discussed during the workshop was **GeoJSON**. This multi-language format supports several geometrical data types which makes it ideal for storing information about polygons and shapes. However, GeoJSON works more efficiently with 2D data, making its application to 3D datasets less clear. An alternative to store 3D shape annotations is **EMDB-SFF**, an open segmentation format that also supports structured biological annotation.

Creating a welcoming home for AI datasets

The BIA seeks to better serve as a community resource by improving how we present and distribute AI data. AI data consumers agreed on the necessity to be able to browse the images and annotations without downloading them to decide what datasets are useful. An approach to this would be to store and serve the data in NGFF and allow download in other widely used file formats such as TIFF. Other features the users considered important to have on the BIA website are links to community tools for data visualisation and annotation, and to allow customised queries to visualise, process, and download parts of a dataset.

Another very popular idea was to provide access to the data via an API, to allow direct data query, transformation, and model training. This approach would relieve some pressure on the need to store data homogeneously, but it would be very important to have clear metadata to make sense of the annotations, and to devise a recommended standard for communicating metadata.

Apart from data presentation and distribution, making data discoverable was one of the priorities for the workshop participants. Some suggestions to increase findability were to allow metadata search, likely via ontologies, and to enable users to find images that look like a supplied example. More generally, the BIA could reach out to scientific journals to position itself as a community resource and explore the possibility of including links to specific datasets in papers. Importantly, unannotated data can be used for un/self-supervised learning, but lack of access to large collections of similar images hinders the development of self-supervised methods. Curating collections of unannotated data on the BIA that can be used for un/self-supervised learning could help advance the development of these methods.

To ensure quality control, datasets must have a unique identifier and metadata versioning has to be allowed as discussed above. The participants suggested that there could be a system in place to indicate when a dataset needs to be updated or improved. Another useful feature would be to use badges to note users that are exceptional contributors or the datasets of extraordinary quality.

A final point of agreement between the participants was the necessity to incentivise the submission of annotation data to the BIA. Some of the measures suggested to recognize the contribution made by annotators have been discussed above, like including authorship as metadata and adding a label to acknowledge users that submit datasets regularly. Other suggestions are to organise annotation challenges (maybe through AI4Life dedicated events), dataset workshops, and training to encourage annotation best practices.

In the near future, the workshop recommendations will be tested on available annotated datasets on the BIA.

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Graphic summary of some of the ideas discussed during the workshop